

Integration of regulatory constraints from a policy database into the energy system modeling tool *atlite*

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Abstract:

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1 Introduction

Energy system optimization models are widely used tools to design and analyze cost-efficient system transformation pathways, identify trade-offs and no-regret solutions, or to investigate the influence of different assumptions and boundary conditions on system characteristics [1]. Such models integrate a broad range of parameters, including technological costs, resource availability, emissions limits, but also implicit representations of socio-political factors like land-use restrictions or limits to the diffusion of new technologies.

Data for technical parameters or cost estimates generally are available from different sources in well-structured form, allowing direct and explicit model integration and transparent discussion of input data setting for energy system optimization models. In contrast, the inclusion of societal or political factors often is more implicitly entangled in the modeling process, for instance through boundary conditions or the choice of specific demand patterns [2]–[5]. Modeling studies with a focus on the influence of such factors thus often cannot draw on already existing data sets, but rather collect and integrate specific data for a specific modeling purpose [6].

As part of the NFDI4Energy Task Area "Integrating Society and Policy in Energy Research", a database called *Environment-related regulations: where can we build what?* can be an example of how to integrate societal or political factors into energy system optimization models. The dataset integrates time series of regulations for energy infrastructure, such as renewable energy generation, in Germany and other European countries. The variables collected include, for example, setback distance, noise limit, shadow flicker limit, turbine height, and other installation requirements.

In this contribution, we showcase the usability of such a policy database by integrating different regulatory constraints on wind power deployment into the energy system modeling tool *atlite* [7]. This Python software package is used to retrieve global historical weather data and convert it into power generation potentials and time series for renewable energy technologies. It is openly available and widely used in energy system models implemented in the framework PyPSA, for instance in PyPSA-Eur [8] or PyPSA-Earth [9].

2 Methods

The database includes legislative policy on restrictions for wind turbine placement both in specific NUTS regions and on the national level. Similar data is integrated in studies quantifying social factors for onshore wind planning, but generally data is collected and evaluated for a specific analysis, and not made more widely available for further modeling purpose [10]. From the modeling perspective, models like PyPSA-Eur include default values for land classes available for wind power installations, without implementing explicit regulation for different regions drawn from a database.

Within *atlite* [7], wind installation restrictions can be modeled using the Exclusion Container. This contains raster and geometry data used to classify land as eligible (or not) for wind turbine placement. For instance, it is possible to model

- required minimum distance from different kinds of residential area by excluding specific CORINE [11] Land Cover classes as raster data with a buffer;
- different maximum allowed distances to nearest motorway (legislative requirement for wind installation maintenance) or minimum required distance away from motorways using geometry data;
- and the exclusion of nature reserves and other protected areas using geometry data.

Specific, regionally resolved regulations can be represented in *atlite* by integrating corresponding restrictions from the policy database through a standardized pipeline. User legislative constraints can be input into a spreadsheet and land eligibility maps based on these constraints are provided as output.

As an exemplary case study, policy restrictions are modelled on a national scale for Greece, Germany, and France. The resulting eligible land area can be compared with the default PyPSA-Eur [8] model configuration, with the corresponding wind generation modelled using ERA5 [12] cutout data. The impact of including these legislative requirements on possible wind power deployment can thus be assessed.

3 Results and conclusion

The exemplary integration of regulatory constraints for wind power deployment from a policy database into *atlite* shows the usability of this data for energy system modeling purposes. By collecting, structuring and publishing such data, the integration of such restrictions as constraints or other factors into the modeling process is facilitated. This allows a more realistic and detailed representation of such regular constraints, in particular for regions with heterogeneous constraints, or for modelling the influence of specific policy choices on feasible and cost-efficient transformation pathways.

Author contributions

Conceptualization, A.C., M.S., R.Q., I.M. ; methodology, H.D., A.C., M.S., R.Q. writing—original draft preparation, H.D., A.C., M.S.; writing—review and editing, H.D., A.C., M.S., R.Q., I.M., J.L.; supervision, M.S., J.L.

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Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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